

Intensified Mineral Carbonation of Natural Canadian Silicates Using Simultaneous Ball Milling

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Abstract

Moving toward net zero emissions require new approaches and technologies, including capturing CO₂ from industrial sources, especially in remote locations where currently using fossil fuels could be unavoidable for generating electricity or machinery for mining, production of cement, steel, hydrogen, gas processing, etc. Mineral carbonation could fix CO₂ in a highly stable solid form. This study explores intensifying the carbonation process of natural Canadian silicates and minerals, kimberlite and wollastonite, which are available in mining sites where the emission occurs. Kimberlite is well-known for containing diamonds. After extracting the diamonds, the value of tailings can vary widely depending on the mineral content and the processing costs, while kimberlite is not as reactive as wollastonite for CO₂ sequestration purposes. This study explored the effects of ball milling and various methods for intensifying the mineral carbonation process for CO₂ sequestration. Calcium and magnesium hydroxides were used as reference materials to assess the effectiveness of the ball-mill reactor. Then, various parameters in the intensification of the carbonation process were investigated, and the effects of additives (sodium hydroxide and magnesium chloride), solvents (pure water and ethanol), and process parameters (temperature, reaction time, and CO₂ level) on carbonation and reaction rate, CO₂ uptake and mineral conversions were investigated. The carbonated samples were subjected to pH testing, calcimetry, XRD analysis and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). For most feedstocks, water as the main solvent led to higher carbonation and precipitating of different carbonates (hydromagnesite, aragonite, calcite, etc.), while for kimberlite, using NaOH led to higher performance. Ball-milling is designed for purposes such as milling, grinding, etc. The centrifugal forces and related phenomena could limit the contraction of CO₂ and other materials in the ball mill jar. However, the results of this study suggest that ball-milling can assist in intensifying mineral carbonation reactions.

Keywords: Process Intensification, Ball Mill Reactor, Mineral Carbonation, Calcium Hydroxide, Magnesium Hydroxide, Wollastonite, Kimberlite, Carbon dioxide, CO₂ Sequestration.

1 Introduction

Moving toward net zero emissions require new approaches and technologies, including capturing CO₂ from industrial sources, especially in remote locations where currently using fossil fuels could be unavoidable for generating electricity or machinery for mining, production of cement, steel, hydrogen, gas processing, etc. Mineral carbonation is the process of fixing CO₂ as carbonates in a highly stable solid form (Mazzotti et al., 2005; Dufourny et al., 2022): silica and insoluble carbonates form by interacting CO₂ with minerals containing metal oxides (Mazzotti et al., 2005), which is so stable that can trap CO₂ for over 100,000 years (Lackner, 2003; F. Wang et al., 2018). Various studies suggest mineral carbonation to mitigate CO₂ emissions (Seifritz, 1990; Nederland et al., 2003; Sanna et al., 2014; Yadav & Mehra, 2021) since this process allows the long-term and safe storage of CO₂ trapped in mineral carbonates which can be used for various applications such as construction, mine reclamation, etc. (Mazzotti et al., 2005).

Mineral carbonation processes are thermodynamically favoured, but inherently sluggish (Doucet, 2011). Naturally, such a reaction occurs in the geological time scale (i.e., silicate weathering) (Mazzotti et al., 2005). Mineral carbonization at industrial scales requires dealing with challenges such as high energy demands, slow and low reactions, production chain and process adaptability complexities, etc. (Santos & Van Gerven, 2011). Also, it is needed to deal with various challenges, such as limiting factors in solving CO₂ and/or silicates in aqueous solution, deficiency of leachable phases and formation of passive layers on the surfaces (Sanna et al., 2014). Moreover, the utilized feedstocks play an important role. For instance, in the mining industry, kimberlite is generally known for containing diamonds. However, after extracting the diamonds, the value of tailings can vary widely depending on the mineral content and the cost of processing them, while kimberlite is not as reactive as wollastonite for CO₂ sequestration purposes. Even for the common high-yield methods, such as controlled thermal activation (dehydroxylation), the temperature exothermicity of the carbonation process is not significant, and the required energy for high-temperature pretreatment is recovered inefficiently. Therefore, many studies focused on the intensification of the carbonation processes (Dlugogorski & Balucan, 2014; Pasquier et al., 2014; Werner et al., 2014, 2013; Hariharan & Mazzotti, 2017; Breuil et al., 2019; Rim et al., 2020; Yadav & Mehra, 2021; Dufourny et al., 2022).

Process intensification (PI) is a key facet of engineering development (Santos et al., 2013) to

develop cheaper, safer, and sustainable technologies using innovative solutions to improve chemical processes, reduce volumes of equipment, required energy or waste generation (Stankiewicz & Moulijn, 2000). PI helps to make technologies smaller, cost-effective, and more efficient, reduce the number of apparatus (Tsouris & Porcelli, 2003), capital and operating costs, and improve the process and chain efficiency, quality, safety, etc. (Drioli, 2007). (Baldea, 2015) concludes the definition of Process intensification as “any chemical engineering development that leads to substantially smaller, cleaner, safer and more energy efficient technology or that combine[s] multiple operations into fewer devices (or a single apparatus).”

Recent studies reported that mechanochemical pre-conditioning could improve the kinetics efficiency and capacity of mineral carbonation and increase the CO₂ uptake capacity up to twice (Ke et al., 2023). In addition to milling, researchers reported the potential of ball milling in making amorphous materials (Takacs, 2002) and separating and storing gasses like hydrogen in the form of powder (Mateti et al., 2022; Blain, 2022). Moreover, studies reported that ball milling could intensify solid-state chemical reactivity in multi-component systems (Takacs, 2002). For instance, a considerable increase is reported in specific surface area and porosity of olivine-rich basalt particles in wet ball milling, which led to increasing CO₂ adsorption. These researchers concluded that defects caused by ball milling in crystal structure facilitated the carbonation of the materials (Rigopoulos et al., 2015). Compared to other approaches, the application of grinding in intensifying mineral carbonation is new and needs to identify and study the governing mechanisms and effective parameters (Dufourny et al., 2022). Therefore, this study focused on the mineral carbonation process intensification of the natural Canadian silicates and hydroxides, kimberlite and wollastonite using the ball mill. Various techniques, including slurry, incubator and pressurized slurry, were investigated. The effects of various additives (sodium hydroxide and magnesium chloride), solvents (pure water and ethanol), and process parameters (temperature, reaction time, and CO₂ level) on carbonation and reaction rate, CO₂ uptake and mineral conversions were investigated.

2 Background

2.1 Mineral carbonation

Since the beginning of the industrial revolution, the steady increase of Carbon dioxide (CO₂)

emissions in the atmosphere has made it among the primary greenhouse gases contributing to global warming, leading to climate change and affecting the ecosystem and biodiversity (Sipilä et al., 2008). In recent years, atmospheric carbon dioxide levels increased dramatically and reached 419 ppm in March 2023 (NASA, 2023). While transferring to renewable energies has already started, reducing emissions and trapping greenhouse gasses could assist in coping with this serious global concern. Various CO₂ storage and sequestration technologies are under research and development, such as ocean storage, geological storage, biological storage, and mineral carbonation (Sipilä et al., 2008; Neeraj & Yadav, 2020).

In nature, atmospheric CO₂ could be fixed when it reacts with silicates as the alkaline and alkaline-earth metals sources through geological time scales (Mazzotti et al., 2005). For instance, studies suggest that plate tectonics has an important effect on atmospheric CO₂ levels: the breakup of Pangaea and an increase in the continents' surface area, or the formation of the Himalayas as a result of the collision of India with Asia plates increased the exposure of silicate rocks to chemical weathering and consumed CO₂ from the atmosphere to form carbonate minerals (Bartoli et al., 2005; Van Der Meer et al., 2014; León et al., 2018; YUE & GAO, 2018; Earle, 2022; Müller et al., 2022). Figure 1 suggests a correlation between mountain building and decreasing the average global temperature during the Cenozoic (66 million years ago until present). According to this figure, the trends of decreasing atmospheric CO₂ levels since the formation of the Himalayas suggests that natural mineral carbonation could be so effective in CO₂ sequestration that led to about a 10°C decrease in the average global temperate and climate change.

Figure 1. Tectonic events during the Cenozoic and the trends of temperature and CO₂. Credits: Steven Earle, CC BY 4.0, based on information from studies by James Hansen and others compiled by Root Routledge (Routledge, 2013; Earle, 2022).

Mineral carbonation follows a similar principle but occurs at a much higher speed than natural weathering: To fix the CO₂ as carbonates, high concentration CO₂ is interacted with metal-oxide-containing materials (Seifritz, 1990; Dunsmore, 1992; Lackner et al., 1995). Calcium and magnesium are considered the most attractive metals (Mazzotti et al., 2005), and their alkaline earth metal oxides and hydroxides are considered ideal feedstocks in the mineral carbonation process due to their high carbonation rates. Solid-phase sources, alkaline minerals, and wastes containing Ca and/or Mg can be other sources. Magnesium, calcium and iron-rich silicates are abundant in the Earth's crust and are common natural feedstocks for carbonation: the reaction of serpentine (Mg₃Si₂O₅(OH)₄) and olivine (Mg₂SiO₄) with CO₂ forms carbonates such as magnesite (MgCO₃), hydromagnesite (Mg₅(CO₃)₄(OH)₂·4H₂O) and nesquehonite (MgCO₃·3H₂O) (Guermeh et al., 2022) and the carbonation of wollastonite (CaSiO₃) forms calcite (CaCO₃) (Dufourny et al., 2022). Magnesite is the most desirable phase in the Mg-carbonates (Swanson et al., 2014; Woodall et al., 2019), considering the 1:1 CO₂ ratio and omitting additional crystalline water. Moreover, magnesite is the most thermodynamically stable carbonate under any conditions. However, the carbonation kinetics of calcic feedstocks is substantially higher, which could be related to the faster precipitation of calcite (CaCO₃) compared to the magnesite (MgCO₃) (Saldi et al., 2013).

Mineral carbonation can be performed via techniques such as in-situ, ex-situ (Mazzotti et al., 2005), direct approaches (gas-solid carbonation, direct aqueous carbonation), and indirect approaches (multistage gas-solid carbonation route, Acetic route, and two-step aqueous carbonation) (Kakizawa et al., 2001; Katsuyama et al., 2005; Huijgen et al., 2005; Sipilä et al., 2008; Sanna et al., 2014; Yadav & Mehra, 2017a, 2017b; Luo & He, 2021) A structure diagram for common mineral carbonation methods is represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Common mineral carbonation methods at a glance (Luo & He, 2021). Reproduced with permission from Springer Nature and license number 5500340995614.

Some studies focused on the effects of various factors in improving carbonation, individually or in combination: the size of particles, temperature, thermal activation, CO₂ pressure, catalysts, pH, chemical additives and carbonation during grinding (Park & Fan, 2004; O'Connor et al., 2001; McKelvy et al., 2006; Gerdemann et al., 2007; Rashid et al., 2019, 2021; Rim et al., 2020). Similar to many processes, the mineral carbonation reaction's efficiency could be affected by various reasons, such as the limiting steps at the reactor level, which include high energy demand, slow kinetics etc. Also, mineral carbonation has limiting steps at the particle level, which can be summed up into three main limiting factors: 1) inappropriate mineral dissolution, 2) CO₂ solvation and hydration, and 3) reaction passivation after precipitation (Huijgen & Comans, 2007; Olajire, 2013; Sanna et al., 2014; Werner et al., 2014; C. Wang & Li, 2018; Neeraj & Yadav, 2020). Several approaches were applied to improve the reaction and address the mentioned limiting factors. The approaches for enhancing the mineral carbonation reaction and some related studies are represented in Table 1.

Table 1. List of some of the enhancement techniques of mineral carbonation.

Enhancement techniques	Principle	Examples of studies
Chemical treatment	Use of acids, bases, and salts as leaching agents to enhance ion extraction and increase CO ₂ absorption.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The effectiveness of using HCl aid to improve serpentine, steel slag, and mining waste dissolution was reported (Dutrillac et al., 2000). - H₂SO₄ was reported as the best leaching agent, followed by HCl, HNO₃, and organic acids (Teir et al., 2007). - Bases used to buffer the system's pH for the carbonation (Arce Ferrufino et al., 2018). - Compared to acids, salts lead to a lower efficiency (Zhang et al., 2020).
Physical treatment	Applying mechanical treatments to the feedstock (such as grinding) and heat treatment ¹ to increase the surface area.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prior heat treatment of serpentine allows it to dehydroxylate and increase the feedstock's available MgO (Schulze et al., 2004). - The optimal temperature for increasing serpentine reactivity was reported as 630°C. Higher temperatures were reported ineffective (O'Connor et al., 2001). - Ball-milling reduced serpentine particle size by up to 88 %, which makes the reaction more cost-effective (Sanna et al., 2013).
Variation in reaction conditions	Increasing temperature and pressure inside the reactor.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing the temperature and/or pressure improves the carbonation. However, it should be increased with caution since the equilibrium is changed at very high temperatures (Hosseini et al., 2015). - Solubility and temperature are inextricably linked in carbonation: CO₂ dissolution is lower at higher temperatures and leads to less available CO₂ in the aqueous phase (Hosseini et al., 2015). - Crystal structure is affected by temperature: as temperature rises, some minerals dehydroxylate (Schulze et al., 2004).
Process intensification	Engineered assessed strategies and techniques to intensify the reaction in a cost-effective way.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Utilizing ultrasound to remove the passivating layers in the slurry reduced the particle size for stainless steel slags. Sonication proved to be an efficient method to improve the carbonate conversion and the reaction rate (Santos et al., 2013). - The reaction is taking place within a reactor that implements the technology of a gravity pressure vessel. The technique proved to be effective in terms of CO₂ sequestration (Santos et al., 2013).

The current study focused on using carbonated Kimberlite to create cement-based building materials under relatively mild conditions, following (Chakravarthy et al., 2020) and (Chai et al., 2021) studies. The process was carried out using thin film and slurry carbonation. The study demonstrated that the process has the potential to sequester CO₂, but not at the desired level. By the way, it seems worthwhile continuing their work under intensified conditions. Also,

¹ Heating of mineral containing hydrated minerals can help increase surface area since the minerals become dehydroxylated and that opens up pores. This can be done by conventional heating and also by microwave heating.

accelerated weathering and carbonation (mild to intensified) of natural Canadian silicates (Kimberlite and Wollastonite) for CO₂ Sequestration from the (Chai et al., 2021) study were investigated.

2.2 Ball Mill

A ball mill is a grinder made of a hollow cylinder that rotates around its axis and utilizes balls as the grinding media. Grinding can perform dry or wet. In conventional ball mills, the balls move up and cascade or drop down due to the rotation of the cylinder, which leads to reducing the size of particles (Figure 3-a).

Planetary ball mills are a variation of ball mills that the grinding jar is mounted on a main rotating sun disk and rotates in the opposite direction around the center of this disk. Such motion grind materials using impact, shearing and friction forces of ball-to-ball and ball-to-wall collisions. The planetary movement subjects materials to the gravity force, such as conventional ball mills, as well as centrifugal and Coriolis forces that increase the grinding parts' kinetic energy (Figure 3-b). Planetary ball mills can be used for wet or dry grinding hard to soft, brittle or fibrous materials and lead to sample homogenization, which reduces analysis errors. The grinding parts must always be harder than the material to be ground to avoid contamination of the samples with undesired abrasion from the grinding parts. Therefore, the materials of grinding jars and grinding balls are chosen based on the hardness of the materials. For instance, grinding parts made of zirconium oxide or agate are used for heavy metals such as chromium, nickel or cobalt. For calcium, grinding parts made of steel can be used (FRITSCH Milling and Sizing, 2013). A simplified schematic of the ball milling process is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A simplified schematic of the ball milling process. (a) Conventional ball mills, (b) Planetary ball mills; F₁: Jar's movement centrifugal force, F₂: Disk's movement centrifugal force, and F₃: Coriolis Force.

3 Objectives

This study investigates the intensification of the carbonation process during ball milling. As discussed, carbonation suffers several issues, including the passivation effect and covering the materials with carbonates and silica that slows the reaction rate and interrupts the process. Figure 4 represents the shrinking core model of wet particle carbonation adopted from (Santos et al., 2013). According to this model, the reacted layer acts as a barrier for the unreacted core and reduces the carbonation reaction's efficiency. Grinding the materials could improve the process not only by breaking the unreacted core and exposing it to the liquid film but also by increasing the surface for reacting materials. Removing diffusion-limiting layers and breaking particles can intensify the mineral carbonation (Santos et al., 2014).

Figure 4. Shrinking core model of wet particle carbonation

Two natural Canadian silicates were studied: wollastonite and kimberlite. Wollastonite is a fast-weathering mineral and contains high levels of lime. Compared with wollastonite, the reaction rate of kimberlite is lower, especially at higher pH ranges where carbonation reactions usually occur. To study ball milling effects in carbonation, fast-reacting minerals are used as a reference for slow-reacting ones. To make comparison easier, calcium and magnesium hydroxides were used as standard fast-reacting materials to ensure that the reactor worked properly. It is known that for the carbonation process, hydroxides react faster than silicates; In hydroxides, calcium reacts faster and easier than magnesium, and in silicates, wollastonite reacts faster and easier than kimberlite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2 > \text{Wollastonite} > \text{Kimberlite}$).

To investigate the intensification of the carbonation process, various additives (sodium hydroxide and magnesium chloride), solvents (pure water and ethanol), and process parameters (temperature, reaction time, and CO_2 level) on carbonation and reaction rate, CO_2 uptake and

mineral conversions were investigated. The carbonated samples were subjected to pH testing, Calcimetry, XRD analysis, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

4 Materials and methods

4.1 Materials

In this study, "wollastonite" refers to the "wollastonite ore" that predominantly contains the wollastonite mineral phase. Wollastonite was supplied by the Ontario mine of Canadian Wollastonite. Using laser diffraction indicated a diameter of less than 25.9 μm for the majority of the sample's particles. Microscopic imaging of the samples revealed an acicular shape and a relatively wide particle size distribution. XRD analysis reveals the presence of wollastonite (CaSiO_3), diopside ($\text{CaMgSi}_2\text{O}_6$), and quartz (SiO_2).

Kimberlite was provided by the DeBeers group, which was sampled and collected from the Gahcho Kué Diamond mine in Canada's northwest territories. The kimberlite tailing was identified as finely processed kimberlite with grain sizes ranging from 3.9 to 62.5 μm . Since the kimberlite sample was wet, it was dried at 110 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours. Microscopic imaging of the material indicated irregularities in particle shapes of varying sizes. XRD analysis of the sample suggested the presence of calcite (CaCO_3), chrysotile ($\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_9$), forsterite (Mg_2SiO_4), microcline (KAlSi_3O_8), montmorillonite ($\text{Al}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}_{12}\text{Si}_4$), phlogopite ($\text{KMg}_3\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$), silicate (SiO_4), and talc ($\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$) in kimberlite tailing.

Calcium hydroxide and magnesium hydroxide were supplied as fine powders and were used as reference materials for wollastonite and kimberlite, respectively.

4.2 Experiment Setup

4.2.1 Ball Mill Reactor

The experiment was carried out in a wet and pressurized ball milling reactor (Retsch PM Grind Control) equipped with gas pressure and temperature sensors with a measurement range of up to 500 kPa, and 0–200 $^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. During grinding, the reaction and process data, pressure and temperature are transmitted wirelessly and monitored using PM Grind Control software. The device supports data measurement rates from 5 seconds to 5 milliseconds.

Milling was carried out using a 250 ml stainless steel grinding jar and stainless-steel milling balls of 3 mm diameter mixed into the wet feedstock (Figure 5). The jar was placed in Planetary Ball Mill PM 100. This device utilizes one grinding station, and the sun wheel to the grinding jar speed ratio is 1:-2. Free Force Compensation Socket (FFCS) technology enables the device to compensate for the vibrations of the mill and pulverizes and mixes various materials (Retsch GmbH, 2019).

Figure 5. Ball mill reactor setup

The experiment was carried out in several stages. First, to evaluate how the reactor works, the system was tested without introducing CO₂ to observe temperature patterns at different time intervals (5 minutes on/5 minutes off). Then the reaction was pressurized by CO₂. The reactor was refilled in case of pressure drop inside the reactor. Then, the timing effects were investigated by experimenting with various reaction times (5, 15, 30 and 60 minutes). Pure water and ethanol were tested as solvents. Also, the additives (0.64M NaOH and a percentage of 16.6 g/L MgCl₂) were then added to evaluate their possible effects on carbonation. MgCl₂ promotes the appearance of aragonite for wollastonite and calcium hydroxide (Santos et al., 2014), and was not tested on kimberlite considering its poor reactivity.

Based on the manufacturer's instructions, one-third of the jar's volume was filled with grinding materials (solids), and 40 mL of ultrapure water was added as the solvent. The reactor was pressurized by CO₂; Then, feedstock was wet-milled and carbonated at the same time inside a grinding jar.

The effects of using ultra-pure water with 25% ethanol in carbonating the samples also were investigated following the investigations that used ethanol as a solvent to promote calcium carbonate synthesis: According to (Ounoughene et al., 2018), adding ethanol to the carbonated lime slurry promotes the carbonation reaction of calcium oxide (CaO) by increasing CO₂ uptake. The authors evaluated various portions and reported that 25% were the most effective. Additionally, (Seo et al., 2005) reported that PCC was the dominant species when water was used as the dominant solvent with diluted ethanol (less than 40%) in the slurry. In contrast, calcite, aragonite, and vaterite were formed when ethanol was used as the primary solvent (more than 60%).

In next step, the effects of additives (sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and magnesium chloride (MgCl₂)) were investigated. NaOH was primarily used to buffer the reaction's pH. MgCl₂ was tested based on (Santos et al., 2013) report about the efficacy of MgCl₂ as an additive to promote aragonite precipitation on aragonite synthesis from wollastonite using ultrasound. Moreover, calcium hydroxide (portlandite) can act as a calcium-leaching agent when mixed with MgCl₂ (Xiang et al., 2006). The reaction between the reactants produces magnesium hydroxide, as shown in equation (1). Magnesium chloride regenerates when CO₂ is added to the solution, and calcium carbonate polymorphs (calcite and aragonite) form, as seen in equation (2).

4.2.2 Carbonated Products Characterization

After completion of the reaction, the balls were separated using a sieving machine, and the collected sample was dried at 105°C in the oven for 25 hours before being stored in plastic test tubes. Then a series of tests, including pH, and calcimetry. Also, non-destructive techniques such as XRD and SEM were applied to characterize and identify the carbonated products as well as milling effects.

4.2.2.1 pH

The pH of samples was measured using a Fisher Scientific accumet AE150 pH meter. The pH meter was calibrated with neutral and basic buffers of 7.00 and 10.01. According to the pH meter instructions, the sample-to-water ratio was set to 1:100, with 2g of sample and 200 ml of distilled water. The pH was measured while the diluted sample was mixed by a magnetic stirrer until the value was stabilized.

4.2.2.2 Calcimetry

Calcimetry is a technique for measuring inorganic carbon in collected samples. The carbonate content of five samples was tested. Each sample was diluted in distilled water after being placed in one of the five sealed Erlenmeyer flasks. Each flask was linked to a graduated water-filled manometer-style column, which measured the volume of released CO₂. A 7 ml tube of 4M HCl was placed in each flask. The vessel was carefully closed with a stopper and shaken to allow the reaction to start and the CO₂ to be released. Shaking continued for 10 to 15 minutes or until the value of the volume released in the burette remained stable.

Prior blank determinations and standards are required for each test series to obtain the reference value and calibrate the apparatus to avoid falsified results (Dudhaiya et al., 2019). According to Eijkelkamp Soil & Water (2022) manual, equation (4) was used to calculate the amount of CaCO₃ in the carbonated samples based on the measured released CO₂ volume (Eijkelkamp, 2022).

$$W_{\text{CaCO}_3} = 1000 \cdot \frac{m_2(V_1 - V_3)}{m_1(V_2 - V_3)} \cdot \frac{100 + W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{100} \quad (4)$$

Where W_{CaCO_3} denotes the carbonate content in grammes of carbonate per kilogramme of sample, m_1 and m_2 denote the mass of the sample and the mean mass of the standard samples, respectively. V_1 , V_2 , and V_3 in millilitres are the volume of CO₂ released by the sample, the mean volume of CO₂ released by the standards, and the mean volume change in the blank determinations respectively. $W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the water content of the dried sample as determined by ISO 11465, expressed in weight percent. Because the samples were already dried after the reaction, $W_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ was zero.

4.2.3 Non-Destructive Tests

Mineral carbonation occurs when the interaction of CO₂ with solid raw resources results in the absorption of CO₂ in an aqueous solution and the dissolution of mineral particles into mineral ions, which then precipitate into a metal carbonate, as previously stated throughout this research. Magnesium or calcium carbonates (MgCO₃ or CaCO₃) are examples of the latter. These inorganic compounds have different crystalline structures: calcite, aragonite, and vaterite for calcium carbonate, and magnesite, nesquehonite, hydromagnesite, and so on for magnesium carbonate (Haque et al., 2019; Chalouati, 2022). Non-destructive techniques could assist in distinguishing, identifying, and examining these carbonates.

4.2.3.1 XRD analysis

The different phases of the carbonated products were identified using a Malvern Panalytical Empyrean XRD Diffractometer. The sample was ground into a fine powder with a pestle before being pressed into a cavity (Figure 6). Then it was positioned and loaded into the reflection-transmission spinner, and the analysis was initiated for 20 minutes (Figure 7). The obtained data is analyzed using High score plus software, which refers to the web mineral database (Barthelmy, 2014), and the diffractograms are created in Excel.

Figure 6. Sample preparation for XRD analysis

Figure 7. Malvern Panalytical Empyrean XRD Diffractometer.

4.2.3.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

The SEM image provides information on mineral rock dissolution (Si leaching) and the formation of calcium or magnesium carbonates, allowing the particle size and morphology of carbonated products to be visualized. SEM enables semi-quantitative analysis of elemental concentrations of individual particles or intra-particle grains, such as Ca, Mg, C, O, and Si, permitting the comprehension of the reaction mechanism.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Process Parameters and Milling

To study the relationship between milling and temperature, the reactor ran with feedstocks without CO₂. According to Figure 8, the reactor generates energy while the reaction is underway. As expected, the calcium hydroxide reaction rate was high, and the temperature reached up to 50.5 °C, which decreased during the 5 minutes off. In a similar period, magnesium hydroxide, wollastonite and kimberlite reached up to 29.8°C, 29.2°C, and 27.6°C, respectively. For these feedstocks, the temperature decreases were not as significant as calcium hydroxide during the 5 minutes off. The effects of the reactor in the reaction could be confirmed considering the fluctuations in temperature when the reactor is operating and when it is turned off.

Figure 8. Temperature (°C) reading for the feedstocks 5 minutes on and 5 minutes off.

In the next step, CO₂ was added to the reaction. For calcium, the temperature increased up to 182 °C, which was relatively high for the reactor. Similarly, the temperature increased up to 82°C for magnesium hydroxide during milling. For Wollastonite, the temperature rose up to 62°C. For Kimberlite, the temperature reached up to 33.3°C. The increase in temperature after introducing CO₂ to the reaction and the differences in this increase could be explained by the theoretical basis: mineral carbonation is exothermic, and the differences can be explained by the different mineral compositions, heat capacities and thermodynamic properties of the different feedstocks (Renforth et al., 2011; Neeraj & Yadav, 2020). Observations on 5 minutes, 15 minutes, 30 minutes, and 1 hour timing intervals indicated that as the reaction time increases, so does the maximum temperature reach for the various feedstocks.

5.2 pH

Adjusting pH values during the reaction process is suggested as an efficient indicator for the reaction's dominated phase (Druckenmiller & Maroto-Valer, 2005; Ukwattage et al., 2016). The dominant production at low pH (≈ 4) is H₂CO₃, at mid pH (≈ 6) is HCO₃⁻, and at high pH (≈ 9) is CO₃²⁻. Therefore, the available carbonate ions at a basic pH promote the precipitation of carbonate minerals.

Figure 9 represents the pH of feedstocks in different conditions. In this table, the pH values of each case can also be compared with other cases graphically using the provided colour bars. Results suggest a pH > 9 for all samples, even for unreacted feedstocks. For all tests, the pH of calcium hydroxide, magnesium hydroxide, wollastonite and kimberlite samples were always over 12.35, 10.05, 9.75 and 9.07, respectively. The maximum pH of 13.22 and 10.91 was observed for calcium and magnesium hydroxides, respectively, in the pressurized reactor. For the tested minerals, the maximum measured pH was 10.34 and 10.24, respectively, for wollastonite and kimberlite when NaOH was used as an additive in the pressurized ball mill reactor.

	Unreacted	Milled	Pressurized	Pressurized + NaOH	Pressurized + MgCl ₂
Calcium hydroxide	13	13.21	13.22	12.41	12.35
Magnesium hydroxide	10.25	10.75	10.91	10.48	10.05
Wollastonite	10	10.32	9.795	10.34	9.75
Kimberlite	9.2	9.41	9.67	10.24	9.07

Figure 9. pH of feedstocks in different conditions.

In comparison with the unreacted materials, results indicate an increase in pH of all milled feedstocks. The highest increase in pH of milled feedstocks was for the magnesium hydroxide by 4.88%, then wollastonite by 3.2%. Kimberlite and calcium hydroxide were in the next levels by 2.28% and 1.62% increase in pH, respectively.

For pressurized samples, the highest increase in pH of milled feedstocks was observed for the magnesium hydroxide by 6.44%, then kimberlite by 5.1%. For calcium hydroxide, pH increased just by 1.62% and for wollastonite pH was decreased.

NaOH as an additive for pressurized reactor led to a significant increase in pH of kimberlite samples (11.3%). For wollastonite and magnesium hydroxide the pH increase was 3.4% and 2.24% respectively. A decrease in pH was observed for calcium hydroxide sample. MgCl₂ as an additive for pressurized reactor led to a pH decrease for all tested samples.

These results do not suggest a specific trend for pH of feedstocks and not a significant change in pH value even after carbonation. The similarity of pH before and after carbonation can be explained by constantly milling and exposing more Alkali-minerals to the solution and thus controlling the pH. (Santos et al., 2013) reported a similar expectation: pH would decrease with

carbonation extent, but if the minerals are less alkaline, the pH change may be smaller. Plus, if the minerals are not evenly carbonated, the pH may be inconsistent, which could occur due to the poor CO₂ contact inside the ball mill (because of low moisture content, plus material accumulating near the walls and corners).

These results also could suggest that it may not be accurate to conclude the carbonation of the feedstock and occurring the reaction just by pH test. It was expected during experiment design, and other tests were predicted for this experiment to quantify how much CO₂ was sequestered, measure the carbonate content of the carbonated samples and identifying the various mineral phases of the products.

5.3 Calcimetry

Calcimetry results are expressed in carbonate content (g/kg). Each feedstock was evaluated with and without additives to see if there was a difference in the carbonation process. Figure 10 represents the carbonate content of each used mineral. In this table, the values can also be compared with other cases graphically using the colour bars.

	Unreacted	Milled	Pressurized	Pressurized + NaOH	Pressurized + MgCl ₂	Pressurized + Ethanol
Calcium hydroxide	55	129	921	396	474	395.3
Magnesium hydroxide	50	59	705	213	164	111.2
Wollastonite	40	49	240.5	151	102	-
Kimberlite	20	23	34	70	-	34.5

Figure 10. Carbonate content (g/kg) of the different feedstocks; Calcimetry results.

Figure 10 indicates that according to calcimetry results, using the ball mill reactor led to a higher carbonate content for all cases in this experiment. These results indicate the highest improvements in the carbonation reaction in the pressurized ball mill reactor when water is used as the main solvent for all cases but kimberlite, which shows a slightly higher carbonated content in the presence of ethanol (34.5 vs. 34 g/kg): over 15.7 times increase in the carbonate content was observed for the most reactive feedstock in this experiment, Ca(OH)₂. This increase was over 13 times for the other reference material, Mg(OH)₂. Similarly, the carbonate content of the fast-weathering mineral, wollastonite, was increased over 5 times. Even for the mineral with the

lowest reactivity, kimberlite, pressurized the ball mill results indicate a 0.7 times increase in the carbonate content. For kimberlite, a slightly higher increase in carbonated content (~0.73 times) was observed in the presence of ethanol.

This figure also suggests that the highest increase in carbonated content for kimberlite (2.5 times) was observed when NaOH as an additive was introduced to the pressurized ball mill reactor. For this reactor, NaOH as an additive also led to a 6.2, 3.2 and 2.77 times increase in the carbonate content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, and wollastonite, respectively.

These results suggest that for $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, using MgCl_2 as an additive led to more carbonate content than NaOH and ethanol (7.6 times vs. 6.2 and ~6.19 times, respectively). Also, MgCl_2 as an additive led to increasing the carbonate content of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and wollastonite by 2.28 and 1.55 times respectively.

Lastly, these results suggest that even milling of the materials respectively led to 1.34, 0.18, 0.22 and 0.15 times increase of carbonate content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, wollastonite and kimberlite.

Calcium and magnesium oxides are the ideal feedstocks since they have the highest reactivity in the carbonation process (Schaef et al., 2011; Galan et al., 2015) and lead to much higher carbonate content than silicates. This experiment led to similar results: calcium hydroxide, the most reactive feedstock, sequestered up to 866 g/kg net of carbonates when pressurized in ultra-pure water, followed by magnesium hydroxide with up to 655 g/kg net, wollastonite with 256 g/kg net, and kimberlite with 50 g/kg net.

For silicates, the difference in reactivity can be explained by the complex mineral composition of kimberlite versus wollastonite, which suggests less effectiveness in carbonation. Also, wollastonite is known to be more reactive than other silicates due to the less tight bound of its Ca atom to valence electron compared to the Mg (Chai et al., 2021).

Moreover, these results suggest different carbonation levels for the feedstocks with and without additives: For calcium hydroxide, using only water was the best option compared to additives. Adding NaOH and MgCl_2 respectively led to a 52% and 48% decrease in the carbonate content.

For magnesium hydroxide, more carbonation was achieved when pressurized with water alone with a net of 655 g/kg, compared to a net of 163 g/kg and 114 g/kg when NaOH and MgCl₂ were added, respectively.

Similarly, for wollastonite, a higher carbonate content was achieved when pressurized in water, compared to adding the additives. In contrast, Kimberlite was carbonated more effectively in the presence of NaOH, and the carbonate content increased from 34 to 70 g/kg.

Ethanol promotes the carbonation reaction and increases CO₂ uptake (Ounoughene et al., 2018). Furthermore, when it is diluted less than 40% in the slurry, PCC will be the dominant specie (Seo et al., 2005). Therefore, this section discusses the various results obtained using 25% ethanol as a solvent. However, this experiment's results suggest no significant impact in ethanol on the carbonate content g/kg or CO₂ wt. percent. Compared with the samples containing 25% ethanol, the carbon content was higher when water was used as the primary solvent. Results also indicate that using ethanol led to almost similar results to adding NaOH to buffer the reaction for the hydroxides. Kimberlite had the highest CO₂ uptake in the presence of NaOH, while using ethanol led to no significant difference compared to pressurizing it in water.

5.4 Non-Destructive Tests

5.4.1 XRD

The products of each experiment were investigated to identify mineral phases formed during carbonation. For each feedstock, the results were compared based on the conditions and used additives. The main goal was to identify the different mineral phases, whether carbonates were forming or not, and to evaluate the hypothesis of using the various additives.

Figure 11 represents the XRD patterns for calcium hydroxide under particular scenarios. Based on this, portlandite was the dominant species in the milled sample, with only a trace of calcite. When the sample was pressurized with CO₂ in ultra-pure water, portlandite peaks significantly decreased while calcite peaks increased. Additionally, aragonite was detected. This can be explained by the high temperature that the reactor reached, which allowed forming of polymorphs.

Figure 11. X-ray diffraction (XRD) diffractogram of calcium hydroxide samples: milled (top left), pressurized in water (top right), pressurized with NaOH (bottom left), and pressurized with MgCl₂ (bottom right)

The sample of pressurized feedstocks in the presence of MgCl₂ did not exhibit any aragonite, which was surprising as the magnesium source is meant to promote the formation of Aragonite. The absence of aragonite could be attributed to an insufficient temperature to precipitate or possibly to a low feedstock conversion rate. Calcite was formed, and portlandite peaks are still prominent, but the calcite ones are not as intense as the sample pressurized in water only. Similarly, the variation in peak intensity was also found in the sample pressurized in the presence of 0.64 M of NaOH. In a nutshell, the sample was pressurized only in water carbonated well, and the conversion was better than the other samples, which agrees with the calcimetry test.

According to Figure 12, testing magnesium hydroxide in the mill suggests Brucite as the main species, with some periclase. The pressurized sample in ultra-pure water precipitated Hydromagnesite as the main precipitate, while brucite (magnesium hydroxide) peaks remained present. The presence of brucite could indicate an incomplete reaction, which could be due to poor mass transfer or limited availability of CO₂.

Figure 12. X-ray diffraction (XRD) diffractogram of Magnesium hydroxide samples: milled (top left), pressurized in water (top right) and pressurized with $MgCl_2$ (bottom).

Observations suggest no significant effect of using additives. Both samples exhibited smaller peaks of hydromagnesite, and the software's primordial quantification indicated a lower quantity in both samples. The domination of hydromagnesite as the primary precipitate could be explained by the ball milling reactor temperature: when the temperature rises above $50^\circ C$, Nesquehonite transforms into hydromagnesite due to water loss in the system (Chalouati, 2022).

These results also suggest more carbonation of the pressurized samples with pure water. However, no complete carbonation could be reported, as Brucite remained present even after the reaction ended.

Wollastonite patterns are represented in Figure 13. The milled sample contained diopside, quartz, wollastonite, and small calcite peaks. When pressurized only in water, the sample showed similar patterns with the presence of dolomite. The presence of dolomite can be explained by the presence of the magnesium and calcium phases in the wollastonite ore and the low temperature ($<50^\circ C$) inside the reactor.

Figure 13. X-ray diffraction (XRD) diffractogram of wollastonite samples: milled (top left), pressurized in water (top right) and pressurized with $MgCl_2$ (bottom)

When pressurized in the presence of $MgCl_2$, the sample did not present any significant change. However, based on the primary quantification of the software, more calcite was detected, and no aragonite was detected. Possibly, the conversion started as the silicates peaks went down, while calcite peaks formed while the temperature was not sufficient for aragonite to precipitate. The presence of dolomite could be confirmed considering calcimetry results, as the pressurized sample had the highest carbonate content compared to the others.

The milled kimberlite had a similar pattern to the unreacted sample of (Chai et al., 2021). Analysis of the sample indicates the presence of chrysotile, forsterite, microcline, montmorillonite, phlogopite, quartz, and talc in kimberlite tailing.

Based on Figure 14, comparing the patterns of the different samples indicates that no new peaks were exhibited in both scenarios (pressurized in only water/in the presence of $NaOH$). However, zooming on each silicate individually shows that most of the peaks dramatically dropped, which suggests the occurrence of a partial conversion. Note that kimberlite is not very reactive compared to other silicates, such as olivine and wollastonite, as it has a more complex composition of minerals than them. Therefore, it was assumed that kimberlite would carbonate less effectively. The calcimetry test indicate better results for kimberlite comparing the (Chai et al., 2021) study that was conducted using the incubator and the high-pressure reactor. The partly carbonatation of kimberlite suggests that it can become more reactive to a certain extent.

Figure 14. X-ray diffraction (XRD) diffractogram of Kimberlite samples: milled (top left), pressurized in water (top right) and pressurized with NaOH (bottom)

In addition, the microcline was gone entirely in the second and third samples. This disappearance can possibly be related to microcline weathering. The K-feldspar weathering is endothermic, so maybe as the ball milling reactor is releasing heat increase it favors the conversion of microcline to kaolinite by dissolving the potassium present in the sample (chemical weathering of feldspars). It is merely a suggestion that may be pursued further.

Overall, kimberlite looked partially carbonated, as the silicate in the unreacted sample disappeared and faded, but no carbonates were observed. These results seems more promising than (Chai et al., 2021) study on kimberlite under mild to intensified conditions which elucidate that kimberlite can be reactive to a certain extent. Based on the XRD results, no aragonite was found in calcium hydroxide or wollastonite samples in the presence of $MgCl_2$.

The XRD patterns of the feedstocks in the presence of ethanol are represented in Figure 15. The sample exhibited portlandite and calcite as the main specie, and no aragonite was detected. In the magnesium hydroxide sample, brucite peaks remained dominant with smaller peaks of hydromagnesite compared to the sample pressurized in water. Reviewing the calcimetry findings indicates that the carbon content is relatively low for this sample, which agrees with the XRD patterns, meaning that the carbonation barely started. For kimberlite, no significant change was observed in patterns, even in terms of the silicates peaks; Most of them remained present, which

means that the carbonation was ineffective. However, fewer peaks in the graphs could suggest fewer phases, which could be related to the potential of ethanol to prevent the crystallization of other carbonates.

Figure 15. XRD patterns of the different feedstocks in the presence of ethanol: calcium hydroxide (top left), magnesium hydroxide (top right) and pressurized kimberlite (bottom)

5.4.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM is typically used to observe carbonated products' particle size and morphology. This goal is challenging to achieve because the products are milled, but performing a few SEM analyses was worthwhile to evaluate the aforementioned results. Calcium hydroxide and magnesium hydroxide typically have hexagonal crystal structures. Investigating calcium hydroxide samples indicated that no structure could be depicted for both milled and pressurized samples in the presence of $MgCl_2$. Figure 16 shows that no significant change has occurred. This is normal because the sample is milled at 500 rpm, which makes detecting the shape more difficult.

On the other hand, the structure of the pressurized sample in water was intriguing. Figure 17 shows the formation of hexagonal needles. These latter are mostly aragonite, which crystallizes in the form of pseudo-hexagonal trilling, according to XRD patterns. Additionally, milled magnesium hydroxide presented a hex shape (Figure 18-A), and the pressurized sample in water differed with the absence of the hex shape and presence of blocky flakes crystals (Figure 18-B), which are hydromagnesite as the sample was filled with this latter hydromagnesite according to

XRD. Pressurized wollastonite in water presented dolomite in the form of saddle-shaped curved (Figure 19).

Figure 16. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of pressurized calcium hydroxide milled (left) and in $MgCl_2$ (right). Note that milling led to very small particles that the crystals are hardly visible even by SEM.

Figure 17. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of pressurized calcium hydroxide and water. Note that milling led to very small particles that the crystals are hardly visible even by SEM.

Figure 18. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of pressurized magnesium hydroxide, milled (left) and in water (right). Note that milling led to very small particles that the crystals are hardly visible even by SEM.

Figure 19. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of pressurized wollastonite and water.

6 Conclusion

This study investigated the intensification of the carbonation process for natural Canadian silicates (kimberlite and wollastonite) to sequester CO₂ using a ball-mill reactor. To ensure the efficiency of the reactor, calcium and magnesium hydroxide were tested as refereed materials for wollastonite and kimberlite, respectively. The reactivity of silicates, their potential as carbonation sinks, and the viability of other enhancement measures to promote the reaction was investigated. Chemical additives (NaOH and MgCl₂) were also tested: NaOH to buffer the reaction as it was reported to be effective in enhancing kimberlite carbonation, and MgCl₂ to enhance the reaction rate and to promote aragonite precipitation for wollastonite and calcium hydroxide. Moreover, the effects of water and ethanol as solvents were investigated, considering the reports about the

effectiveness of ethanol in promoting carbonation by increasing the CO₂ uptake, favoring the precipitation of calcium carbonate and purifying the sample by preventing the crystallization of other carbonates.

Testing the reference materials (calcium and magnesium hydroxides) and the fluctuations in temperature when the reactor is operating and when it is turned off indicates the effects of the ball-mill reactor in the carbonation process. Higher carbonation reactivity was observed for wollastonite than kimberlite, which is aligned with the theoretical basis as well as the literature about using other routes of mineral carbonation.

Results suggest that, as was expected, it may not be accurate to conclude the carbonation of the feedstock and occurring the reaction just by pH test for this experiment. Therefore, calcimetry tests were conducted to measure inorganic carbon in collected samples. In addition, XRD and SEM were used to investigate the mineralogical transformations and visualize the crystal phases that occur during carbonation, respectively.

According to calcimetry results, the highest improvements in the carbonation reaction were observed in the pressurized ball mill reactor when water was used as the main solvent for all cases but kimberlite, which shows a slightly higher carbonated content in the presence of ethanol. The highest increase in carbonated content for kimberlite was observed when NaOH as an additive was introduced to the pressurized ball mill reactor.

In theory, using NaOH could assist in more CO₂ absorbance into the aqueous phase. However, results indicate that in this experiment, adding NaOH led to a reduction in reaction rate, which seems to be related to the increasing pH that reduced the solubility of the minerals. Insufficient and/or improper filling may also be contributed to reducing CO₂ dissolution. It could also be attributed to the additionally used chemicals and solvents, which decreased the CO₂ solubility in contrast to their predicted impact and became a significant mass transfer limiting factor that consequently reduced the conversion rate.

The results of pressurized reactors also suggest that for calcium hydroxide, using MgCl₂ as an additive led to more carbonate content than NaOH and ethanol. Also, MgCl₂ as an additive increased the carbonate content of Mg(OH)₂ and wollastonite. Also, results suggest that even

milling of the materials led to a slight increase in the carbonate content of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, wollastonite and kimberlite.

XRD patterns showed precipitation of different carbonates that were further confirmed and visualized with the SEM. Kimberlite did not exhibit any carbonates, but the fading of the original phases presented in the unreacted sample indicates partial carbonation. Despite the kimberlite's poor reactivity and XRD outputs, the carbon contents improvements seem promising compared to (Chai et al., 2021) study, which was conducted with wollastonite and kimberlite using different routes.

SEM results indicate that milling led to very small particles that the crystals are hardly visible even by SEM. These results suggest that the reactor was working, milling occurred, but the mixing was not considerable. Reaching a good combination between mixing and milling is essential to achieve high carbonation. However, the results seem promising since the ball mill is not designed for mixing the three phases of the reaction. It was not possible to observe what was going on inside the reactor, but it was assumed that the CO_2 was not evenly mixed, so only the top layer was pressurized, or the slurry was not sufficiently diluted for CO_2 to dissolve.

A thorough environmental impact and economic feasibility study of this method is recommended for future research work. For instance, the obtained carbonated mineral is in a paste form which makes recovering the chemicals harder. Therefore, recycling and recovering the chemicals is an environmental issue that requires further studies. Moreover, a comparison study of the different routes in terms of cost, energy, environmental concerns and carbonation potential should be conducted to opt for the most fruitful and efficient ones.

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